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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Reducing Energy Consumption in Robotic Processes Using a Single-DOF Bennett Mechanism

TOMÁŠ POŠTULKA¹, DANIEL HUCZALA², GRZEGORZ ORZECZOWSKI³,
AKI MIKKOLA^{1,3}, ZDENKO BOBOVSKÝ¹, AND RÓBERT HUŇADY¹

¹Department of Robotics, VSB–Technical University of Ostrava, 70800 Ostrava, Czech Republic

²Unit of Geometry and Surveying, University of Innsbruck, 6020 Innsbruck, Austria

³Department of Mechanical Engineering, LUT University, 53850 Lappeenranta, Finland

Corresponding author: Tomáš Poštulka (tomas.postulka@vsb.cz)

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ABSTRACT This paper explores the energy-saving potential of a spatial, single-degree-of-freedom (1-DOF) Bennett mechanism in industrial pick-and-place tasks. In comparison to conventional robotic arms with multiple actuators, Bennett’s mechanism uses a closed kinematic structure and a single actuator to realize complicated spatial trajectories. Through both simulation and experimental comparison with a commercial UR3e collaborative robot, the mechatronic prototype of the Bennett mechanism demonstrated a reduction in energy consumption of up to 92% for identical tasks. The results confirm that closed loop mechanisms can be an energy-efficient option for tasks with simple, repetitive motion. While the Bennett mechanism is limited to predefined trajectories, its simplicity, low energy footprint, and suitability for repetitive tasks make it a promising alternative for dedicated automation scenarios. This study underscores the value of low-redundancy kinematic designs in future industrial robotics.

INDEX TERMS Bennett mechanism, spatial four-bar, closed-loop kinematics, energy consumption, pick-and-place automation, single degree of freedom (1-DOF), mechatronic design, UR3e robot.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the key directions in contemporary mechatronic and engineering research is improving energy efficiency in manufacturing processes, with particular emphasis on optimizing robotic systems [1], [2], [3], [4]. Conventional approaches to improve efficiency include the refinement of robotic applications, such as pick-and-place operations, where reduced cycle times and improved motion planning are often prioritized [5], [6], [7]. Recently, however, there has been a growing interest in alternative concepts that achieve the desired motion with reduced kinematic complexity and lower energy demands [8]. By decreasing the number of degrees of freedom (DOFs), it is possible to design mechanisms with closed kinematic chains that are capable of performing complicated spatial tasks while relying only on a minimal number of actuated

motion axes. This approach not only contributes to improved energy efficiency, but also offers benefits such as simplified control algorithms [9], reduced mechanical complexity, and potentially lower manufacturing costs.

A notable example of such a mechanism is the Bennett mechanism [10], one of the simplest spatial mechanisms with a closed loop structure and a single degree of freedom (1 DOF). Despite being actuated by only one motor, it is capable of generating non-trivial spatial trajectories, making it an interesting candidate for industrial applications that typically rely on multi-actuated systems. The mechanism consists of four rotary joints connected by four rigid links arranged in a single closed loop. Although the Bennett mechanism is overconstrained [11], its geometric construction allows it to achieve continuous motion in a three-dimensional space. This feature, combined with its minimal actuation requirements, positions it as a promising alternative to traditional serial manipulators.

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However, the application of such a theoretically motivated multibody system in real-world industrial contexts remains challenging. Several design and implementation aspects must be addressed, including the synthesis of feasible trajectories, the avoidance of internal collisions, and the mechanical robustness under load. An important advantage of the Bennett mechanism is that its motion can be parameterized using rational functions, specifically as quadratic curves in the special Euclidean space $SE(3)$. This property significantly facilitates the design process, for example, one may specify three poses [12] or five desired points [13] in 3D space and compute the corresponding motion curve $C(t)$ using dual quaternion algebra. Established synthesis methods, such as those described in [12], [14], and [15], can be used as they are implemented in open-source software tools such as the Rational Linkages package [16]. Rational parameterization also enables the design of mechanisms with guaranteed non-self-intersecting motion paths [17] and simplifies trajectory planning and the direct kinematics problem [9].

These state-of-the-art methods provide a straightforward way for custom synthesis and design of the closed loop mechanisms, which can efficiently serve as single-purpose devices capable to perform complicated spatial trajectories.

The novelty of this work lies in providing the first experimental comparison between a spatial single-DOF Bennett mechanism and a commercial collaborative robot performing identical pick-and-place tasks. While previous research has focused on optimizing the energy consumption of serial manipulators or analysing alternative low-DOF and parallel mechanisms, no prior study has experimentally evaluated a closed-loop mechanism synthesized directly from a rational $SE(3)$ trajectory and compared it with an industrial robot under the same operating conditions. The Bennett mechanism was selected because it represents the simplest spatial one-DOF closed-loop linkage capable of generating non-trivial 3D motion, and its geometry can be derived directly from a small set of target poses using established interpolation and factorization techniques. This makes it an ideal benchmark for investigating how far a minimal-actuation mechanism can reduce energy consumption in repetitive industrial processes.

This article deals with the design of a single-purpose manipulation device and the evaluation of its energy consumption in relation to a commercially available robotic system. The manipulator is designed as a mechatronic system with one degree of freedom and a closed kinematic structure inspired by the basic Bennett mechanism with four rotational joints. The aim of the article is to present this system as an energy-efficient alternative to robots, which are used in industry even for relatively simple operations. It will be shown that for tasks such as “pick-and-place,” it is possible to replace the robot with a simpler mechanical system and that this system can be designed to take into account the requirements of a specific operation, e.g., obstacle avoidance or orientation of the manipulated object. The design procedure is presented in the article using the example of a prototype, which is later

used in experimental measurements. Its basic kinematics are derived from simulations focused on preliminary assessment of energy consumption of simplified models. Subsequently, the mechanical design is developed into the final form of a functional prototype.

Parallel mechanisms are generally known for their higher energy efficiency compared to serial architectures [18], mainly due to their lower moving mass and more favorable force transmission properties. The objective of this study is to verify whether these theoretical benefits hold true for the Bennett mechanism under realistic operational conditions. The practical part of the article therefore focuses on comparing the energy consumption of the designed prototype and the commercially available UR3e collaborative robot [19], which serves as a well-established benchmark among serial robotic manipulators used in industry. In terms of applicability, it is important to note that the Bennett mechanism is a specific system with a single application and a single trajectory, while the UR3e is a universal robot for general use. Energy consumption assessments (both at the simulation and experimental measurement levels) were performed to evaluate how different trajectory orientations and payload configurations affect the energy requirements of the system. The results achieved contribute to a deeper understanding of the industrial applicability of closed-loop kinematic structures and provide a basis for their further development as low-redundancy, energy-efficient robotic systems.

The pick-and-place task addressed in this article was chosen because of its representativeness within robotic processes and because it is applicable in conjunction with the Bennett mechanism. This is an operation that typically requires high speed, precision, and repeatability. To illustrate the practical implementation of the Bennett mechanism for this type of task, a publicly available video [20] provides a demonstration of its use. The aim of the demonstration is to highlight the potential of single-loop kinematic mechanisms for real-world applications and to support the conclusions presented in this article.

II. INITIAL SIMULATION OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION

Before starting the experimental measurements, a preliminary simulation of energy consumption for three different industrial robot applications (see Figure 1), specifically three trajectories representing pick-and-place operations, was performed. The aim of this simulation was to provide a general estimate of the energy consumption of these tasks for the UR3e Robot and the Bennett mechanism.

These three examples of original robot trajectories are differ from each other and can be seen in the Figure 1. The first trajectory allows the manipulated object to be grasped vertically and then placed in a nearly horizontal position. The goal is to pick up a part from a pallet and then place it on a conveyor belt (that is moving continuously). The second trajectory describes a movement in which the manipulated object is lifted to the upper position in a defined manner

and then placed in a different manner. The third variant is a combination of the previous two approaches. The object is lifted vertically but placed in a specified orientation.

In every case of the three tasks specified above, the UR3e robot performed each using two different motions (Figure 1). The first motion followed the original trajectory, representing a conventional industrial solution, while the second followed an interpolated curve (the motion has the same start, end, and middle positions).

The Bennett mechanism moved only along the interpolated curve, keeping the position and orientation at the defined points (start, end, and middle point).

For each task given by 3 poses, a unique Bennett mechanism exists which kinematics can achieve those poses [12]. This means that the movement along the interpolated trajectories presented on Figure 1 is ensured by three different

kinematic structures of Bennett’s mechanism and with three different motion curves $C_{1..3}(t)$.

The start and end poses are the same for each type of trajectory within a single task. The middle point is selected from the original trajectory with the aim of getting the interpolated curve as close as possible to the original one. In our case, this was done manually. These three basic points are shown in the Table 1.

TABLE 1. Three main waypoints of the simulated trajectories.

Point	Coordinate [mm]	Trajectory		
		n.1	n.2	n.3
A	x	0.0	115.0	0.0
	y	0.0	-150.0	0.0
	z	0.0	1.0	0.0
Middle Point (M)	x	567.7	467.8	177.0
	y	30.6	-48.0	-18.0
	z	115.3	59.6	203.0
B	x	635.0	56.0	378.0
	y	3.5	-32.0	125.0
	z	0.0	63.0	-100.0

(a) Trajectory n.1

(b) Trajectory n.2

(c) Trajectory n.3

FIGURE 1. Original movement of UR3e (black dashed polyline) and curve interpolated for synthesis of Bennett mechanism (green).

The control of both systems is set with identical values for speed and acceleration of the end point. This was obtained by the following process.

The waypoints (Table 1) from the individual original trajectories were interpolated using a rational curve in the Special Euclidean group in 3D (SE(3)), which produced a smooth, mathematically exact parameterization. This was done using motion interpolation according to the method implemented by the Rational Linkages framework [16], [21]. This curve $C(t)$ was then factorized to generate the kinematic structure of a single-degree-of-freedom Bennett mechanism [14].

The Denavit-Hartenberg (DH) parameters of the mechanism obtained in this way were used to create a simulation model of the mechanism (Figure 3) in Creo Parametric environment. During the simulation process, the parameters of the mechanism servo motor (speed, acceleration) were set to ensure that the motor would not be overloaded. Then, in the simulation, the position and orientation of the endpoint of the mechanism (end effector) were read.

These information was used as input for controlling the UR3e robot. This ensured identical conditions for both systems. The inverse kinematics of the UR3e robot were not calculated; instead, the manufacturer’s built-in inverse kinematics solver was used. This allowed the system to be controlled directly by the position of the end point.

For these energy simulations, several simplifying assumptions were used. For the UR3e, actuator efficiency was not modeled because the robot model provides its electrical energy consumption directly. For the Bennett mechanism, mechanical work was converted to electrical energy using the nominal efficiency specified by the actuator manufacturer. Frictional losses and regenerative effects were

omitted, and negative mechanical work was treated as non-recoverable. These simplifications ensure a consistent comparison, although they may affect the absolute values of the reported energies.

A. SIMULATION PROCESS-UR3e

There are scientific modeling approaches that can provide us with very accurate estimates of power consumption [22]. But for purposes of this study (to analyze the energy consumption of the UR3e robot), a simulation software URSim 5.12.6 [23], designed directly by the robot manufacturer, was more than sufficient.

For each trajectory (original and interpolated trajectory), two simulations were performed, one in the unloaded state and one with a 2.5 kg object placed on the robot interface.

FIGURE 2. Visualization of UR3e and interpolation trajectory n.1.

The energy consumption values under load were then reduced by the amount of energy consumed by the unloaded system in order to obtain the energy consumption corresponding only to the movement of the manipulated object itself – unaffected by the dynamics of the system. This was done to make the resulting values comparable, as the two systems are fundamentally different. The UR3e robot was left in its normal settings and was not restricted in its range of motion, acceleration, or speed. The speed of movement along the trajectory by the robot was set with respect to the following dynamic simulation with the mechanism. To ensure identical velocity profiles, the motion of the mechanism described below was assumed.

To control the URSim, built-in Real-Time Data Exchange (RTDE) communication was used, and our own software written in C++ code (the visualization of the UR3e robot is shown in Figure 2). Communication was performed at a frequency of 250 Hz. The software controlled the robot's position (the endpoint) while simultaneously reading the joint variables and energy consumption data for each joint.

B. SIMULATION PROCESS-Bennett MECHANISM

The dynamic simulation of the Bennett mechanism was performed using PTC CREO Parametric software and the integrated Mechanism module, which allows kinematic and dynamic analysis of mechanical systems. This CAD software was chosen for its ability to realistically simulate movement under defined conditions and to speed up simulation work.

In order for the simulation to take into account only the dynamics of the manipulated object at the end point of the mechanism, similar to the case of a robot, it was necessary to exclude the influence of the mass and moments of inertia of the mechanism on the resulting energy consumption. For this reason, the mechanism model consisted of four simple massless links, and no passive resistances were included. The manipulated object was modeled as a homogeneous sphere with a diameter of 100 mm and a mass of 2.5 kg, representing a typical industrial payload. A visualization of the Bennett mechanism model in CAD software can be seen in Figure 3.

FIGURE 3. Simplified mechanical design of the Bennett mechanism for performing simulations.

The movement of the mechanism was limited by the parameters of the actively driven revolute joint to a maximum speed of 80 deg/s with an acceleration of 80 deg/s². The actuator efficiency was set according to the parameters specified in the data sheet [24] of the actuator that will be used in real measurements, but it reached a maximum of 40%. Gravity acceleration was included in the simulation to act in the negative Z-axis direction (see Figure 1).

The simulation was performed with a sampling frequency of 250 Hz. During the simulation, when the manipulated object moved along the interpolated trajectory, the time histories of the torque and velocity of the active joint were obtained, which were used to calculate the energy consumption.

C. SIMULATION RESULTS

The resulting values for one operational cycle are presented in Table 2. The values in table show the electrical energy

TABLE 2. Simulation of electrical energy consumption per one cycle of motion for UR3e and Bennett mechanisms.

Energy consumption [J]	Trajectory		
	n.1	n.2	n.3
Bennett mechanism	106.3	47.89	83.91
UR3e original trajectory	1 014	1 323	611.1
UR3e interpol. trajectory	1 673	1 306	1 187

FIGURE 4. Graphical illustration of data from Table 2 - Simulation of elec. energy consumption per one cycle of motion for UR3e and Bennett mechanisms.

consumption in Joules for one cycle of movement from point A to point B and back, for only a manipulated object with a mass of 2.5 kg without the influence of system dynamics.

The simulation results give no deviations between cycles. Accordingly, the standard deviation is not presented. According to the data obtained in Table 2 and Figure 4, we can observe a significant decrease in energy consumption in the case of single-loop mechanisms. The energy consumption of the mechanism achieves on average 90% better results compared to standard robot movement.

The second trajectory (Figure 1(b)) was chosen for further investigation in an experiment because of the largest difference between the values from the simulation of energy consumption.

It is possible to assume that in the experimental measurements the energy consumption of the Bennett mechanism will increase due to the deformation of the individual links and additional friction, which was not accounted in the simulation.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Experimental measurements were carried out in a controlled laboratory setting. The original simplified mechanical design from the simulation was modified to the mechatronic prototype form shown in Figure 6. As with the simulation, the UR3e robot was used for real measurements, see Figure 7.

It is important to note that the Bennett mechanism prototype and the UR3e robot differ fundamentally in both workspace and intended use. The UR3e is a universal 6-DOF manipulator with a large 3D workspace and six integrated

high-power actuators, capable of reaching arbitrary poses through software-defined motion.

In contrast, the Bennett mechanism uses only a single actuator and four links arranged in a closed loop. Its workspace is restricted to a predefined spatial curve generated from the original robot motion, and its behavior is determined by the geometric dimensions of the links.

Although both systems operate with similar payloads (up to 3 kg), their actuator size, link geometry, achievable workspace, and operational flexibility differ substantially. This highlights that the Bennett mechanism is not a universal manipulator, but rather a highly efficient single-purpose alternative for repetitive motion.

A. DESCRIPTION OF THE Bennett MECHANISM

The investigated mechanism shown in Figure 6 consists of a single actuated joint, powered by the Dynamixel XH540-V270-R servomotor [24] and three passive joints (more information in Table 3).

The built-in current sensor and encoder ensure complete data reading from the selected servomotor. The control itself is implemented via the Dynamixel SDK (Software Development Kit) directly from the drive manufacturer. The Dynamixel SDK supports a variety of programming languages, but in this study, a Python script was used. The PID control parameters of position control were set as $P = 1800$, $I = 800$, $D = 50$. These values were obtained by manually tuning the system.

TABLE 3. Key technical parameters of Bennett mechanism prototype.

Parameter	Value
Degrees of freedom (DOF):	1
Payload capacity:	3 kg
Reach:	192 mm
Weight:	2.7 kg
Joint range:	$\pm 360^\circ$
Maximum end effector speed:	1.5 m/s
Maximum active joint velocity:	200 deg/s
Power consumption:	55 W (max.)
Current sensor sensitivity:	± 2.69 mA
Encoder sensitivity:	4096 pulse/rev

The data shown in table were collected from the actuator datasheet [24] and measures in a laboratory environment.

The structure consists of two aluminum alloy profiles with a straight geometry, while the remaining two links were fabricated using Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) technology. The 3D-printed components, produced by the Prusa MK3 printer, were manufactured from PETG material with 100% infill to ensure high structural integrity and precision.

Rotating movement between individual links is ensured by a pair of SKF 626-2Z ball bearings mounted with an overlap in the joints (see Figure 5). The load-bearing shaft of the joint consists of a fitted screw (ISO 7379 M5 f9 6 \times 50 – 12.9) that fits into the bearing with high precision and is mounted with an overlap in the body of the link.

FIGURE 5. Cut through the passive joint of the mechanism.

The Bennett mechanism for the chosen (n. 2) trajectory can be described by Denavit-Hartenberg (DH) parameters, which are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4. DH parameters of Bennett mechanism.

i	θ [deg]	d_i [mm]	a_i [mm]	α_i [deg]
P_1	θ_1	0	192.31	143.14
P_2	θ_2	0	320.57	90.40
P_3	θ_3	0	192.31	143.14
P_4	θ_4	0	320.57	90.40

Based on these DH parameters, a line model was first created and then extended into a three-dimensional model (see the Figure 3). This basic model was further developed into its final form adapted for 3D printing. This means that the individual links were divided into smaller sections, which enabled high-precision manufacturing. The static link consists of an aluminum profile sized 40 × 40 mm, which ensures high rigidity of the base. The second link also consists of an Item profile, but with dimensions of 20 × 20 mm. The actual form of the mechanism prototype is shown in Figure 6, which illustrates the weight distribution during measurements with 2 kg loads.

FIGURE 6. Prototype of Bennett mechanism with weights.

The angular positions of the revolute joints of the mechanism, represented by the angles θ_i , change dynamically

during motion [10], because it depends on rational parameterization. The kinematic analysis of the general spatial 4R Bennett mechanism is addressed in detail in [25]. The direct and inverse kinematics problems also with trajectory planning, can be calculated according to [9]. The additional weight is placed with respect to the position of the center of gravity in the middle plane of the second link.

The end effector trajectory of the mechanism on Figure 6 was defined by a quadratic dual quaternion curve $C(t)$, obtained through interpolation of three target poses (initial, intermediate, and final) in SE(3). When rounded to 3 decimal places, it has the form

$$C(t) = \begin{bmatrix} t^2 - 0.923t + 0.226 \\ -0.116t + 0.053 \\ -0.001t - 0.010 \\ -0.039t + 0.018 \\ -0.002 \\ -0.011t + 0.006 \\ -0.020t + 0.007 \\ -0.016t + 0.008 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where the pose on the curve $C(t)$ is given directly by the parameter t , which varies from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$ and encodes the driving joint position angle (see [9, Sect. 3.1] for more details). Kinematically, the factorization [14] of the motion defines a mechanism with the Denavit-Hartenberg (DH) parameters specified in Table 4.

B. DESCRIPTION OF THE UNIVERSAL ROBOT UR3e

The UR3e shown in Figure 7 is a compact robotic arm developed by Universal Robots for collaborative applications. It is designed for applications requiring high precision and flexibility, such as assembly, pick-and-place operations [19], and quality inspection.

The UR3e universal robot was used for the measurements for several reasons. It is a robot that is commonly used in industry for pick-and-place operations with lighter objects and its operating load is similar to the load for which the Bennett mechanism prototype is designed. The robot has a simple communication interface and the manufacturer supplies a virtual environment for performing motion simulations. Its key technical parameters are summarized in Table 5.

TABLE 5. Key technical parameters of UR3e [26].

Parameter	Value
Degrees of freedom (DOF):	6
Payload capacity:	3 kg
Reach:	500 mm
Weight:	11.2 kg
Joint range:	± 360° for most joints
Maximum TCP speed:	1 m/s
Maximum joint velocity:	180 to 360 deg/s
Power consumption:	350 W (average)

The UR3e robot features a lightweight design, allowing it to be mounted on workbenches or integrated

into production lines. The robot utilizes high-precision encoders and virtual torque sensors, enabling safe human-robot collaboration. The arm’s 360-degree joint rotation provides better maneuverability, making it suitable for confined workspaces. The UR3e supports standard industrial instructions for robot movement like *MoveL* (moving in a straight line between specified points) or *MoveJ* (with optimized joint movement so that all joints complete their movement at the same time) [26].

FIGURE 7. UR3e robot arm with weights.

An aluminum modular profile was used to mount the additional weight on the UR3e robot, respecting the same weight location as for the measurements of the Bennett mechanism.

The integrated Real-Time Data Exchange (RTDE) interface protocol was used to read data from the UR3e robot, providing a way to synchronize external applications with the UR controller over a standard TCP/IP connection without compromising the real-time properties of the UR controller [23].

IV. MEASUREMENT METHODOLOGY

For the experimental measurements, an energy consumption comparison was implemented for the motion shown in Figure 1(b). When the motion occurs from the lower to the upper position (marked $A_2 \rightarrow B_2$) around an obstacle and back. The motion along whole defined trajectory was measured.

The first part of the measure was realized on the robot UR3e (Figure 7). Three types of trajectories of the robot’s end effector were measured, as can be seen in Figure 8. The first movement was along the robot’s original trajectory using *MoveL* through 5 marked points. The second movement was performed along an interpolated curve, identical to the movement of Bennett’s mechanism end point. The third

FIGURE 8. Three types of trajectories for universal robot UR3e.

motion was designed based on simulation results, which indicated that the mechanism could achieve significantly lower energy consumption for the specified task. Therefore, this motion was optimized to its theoretical minimum: a direct, shortest-possible path from point A to B, following the removal of the obstacle and using the robot’s *MoveJ* command. For each measurement, the robot was loaded with a weight of 2.5 kg.

During these experiments on the UR3e robot, energy consumption data of each single joint of the arm was collected. The measurements were performed with a sampling frequency of 250 Hz. The energy consumption of the joint was calculated for each joint separately. Subsequently, the results were summed to obtain the total consumption per cycle. The absolute value of the current was used for the calculation because the negative sign only indicates the opposite direction of the robot drive shaft load.

FIGURE 9. Schematic representation of the endpoint movement of the Bennett mechanism.

The energy consumption of the Bennett mechanism was continuously tracked using an integrated current sensor within the actuator. The sampling frequency was approximately 18 Hz. Subsequently, electric current measurements were performed during 20 motion cycles for the motion path

(see Figure 9), imitating a pick-and-place application with a weight of 2.5 kg.

The points P_1 to P_4 indicate the position of the joint of the mechanism, and P_{end} indicates the end effector of the mechanism. The black dotted line shows the circular motion of P_1 and P_2 in space. The trajectory (marked $A_1 \rightarrow B_1$) corresponds to the motion of the end effector of the mechanism when the actively driven joint (located at point P_0) moves within the range $\theta_1 = -150^\circ$ to 158° .

A. MEASURING THE EFFECT OF TRAJECTORY ORIENTATION

The main experiment was extended to include trajectory orientation measurements on the UR3e robot and the Bennett mechanism to compare how the system responds to the changed orientation of the trajectory. Experiments were conducted for three different initial orientations.

TABLE 6. Orientation of the base link of the mechanism during measurement.

Orientation	Yaw [deg]	Pitch [deg]	Roll [deg]
O ₁	0	0	0
O ₂	45	0	0
O ₃	0	90	0

FIGURE 10. Initial orientations of the mechanism. (X-axis - red, Y-axis - green and Z-axis - blue).

In the first orientation, the base link was positioned horizontally, and the actuated link moved within the vertical XZ plane, and this orientation is the same as the orientation of the first measurement. In the second orientation, the base link remains horizontal but was rotated by 45° about the X-axis. In the third orientation, the base link was positioned vertically, with the actuated link moving again in the vertical XZ plane. The orientations tested are summarized in Table 6 and in Figure 10.

To get a better understanding of the system’s orientation, the gravitational acceleration is located in the negative direction of the Y-axis (green arrows) in Figure 10.

All measurements were performed only on the interpolated trajectory and again 20 cycles of movement were performed for each orientation. At the same time, measurements were made with several masses of the object manipulated (0 kg, 1.0 kg, 1.5 kg, 2.0 kg and 2.5 kg).

V. RESULTS AND CALCULATION

The time-based data, such as current and voltage, was collected from the active joints of both systems under test. This data was used to calculate the average energy consumption per one cycle of motion according to the formula

$$E_m = \frac{\sum(UI \Delta t)}{n}, \tag{2}$$

where E_m is the energy corresponding to the given mass of the weights, Δt is the sampling period, I is the current in the actuator, U is voltage, and n is the number of cycles. For UR3e, the total energy consumption was calculated as the sum of the energy consumption of the individual active joints.

To ensure comparability of the results of the two different systems, the E_m values were reduced by the energy E_0 consumed by the no-load system (see Figure 11) as follows

$$E_{cycle} = E_m - E_0. \tag{3}$$

This step makes it possible to compare the data obtained from different systems and the simulation earlier.

TABLE 7. Comparison of energy consumption per one cycle, clear weight 2.5 kg and orientation O₁.

Energy consumption	Experiment [J]
Bennett mechanism	20.1 ± 1.3
UR3e - straight traj.	606.2 ± 9.4
UR3e - original traj.	1 672 ± 32.9
UR3e - interpol. traj.	1 573 ± 49.7

FIGURE 11. Graphical illustration of data from Table 7 - comparison of energy consumption per one cycle, no-load system, orientation O₁.

Significant differences can already be observed between the energy consumption of the Bennett mechanism and that of the industrial robot UR3e. This is an expected result considering the very different kinematics of the system

including the higher number of degrees of freedom of the UR3e. The significant difference in the total mass of the systems probably also has a negative effect on the result, in terms of the higher energy consumption of UR3e. A comparison of identical (interpolated) trajectories reveals an almost tenfold increase in energy consumption required for motion with UR3e.

A comparison of the average energy consumption E_{cycle} of both systems loaded by the 2.5 kg weight. UR3e robot moving along three different trajectories, as shown in Figure 8, and Bennett mechanism moving along an interpolated trajectory, as shown in Figure 9.

The measurement values are reduced by the energy consumption required to operate the system itself without additional load E_0 . And the final results E_{cycle} are shown in Figure 12. According to the shown data, it can be noticed that Bennett's mechanism has 90% less energy consumption to perform a given movement, even though the UR3e robot moves in the shortest and most efficient way (although in reality an impossible movement). For the other movements compared, the difference in energy consumption is even more significant.

TABLE 8. Comparison of energy consumption per one cycle, clear weight 2.5 kg and orientation O_1 .

Energy consumption	Experiment [J]
Bennett mechanism	84.5 ± 11.5
UR3e - straight traj.	622.8 ± 14.0
UR3e - original traj.	1 296 ± 20.8
UR3e - interpol. traj.	1 273 ± 38.7

FIGURE 12. Graphical illustration of data from Table 8 - comparison of energy consumption per one cycle, clear weight 2.5 kg and orientation O_1 .

The significant difference in energy consumption between the UR3e robot and the mechanism is mainly due to the different number of actively controlled joints, different supply voltage levels, but most of all the completely different mechanical design of the systems. A closed loop design allows the load to be partially transferred from the object of manipulation to the joints during movement, and thereby reduces the energy consumption. On the other hand, a serial robot structure has to compensate for the load during the whole movement.

Another important difference is that the Bennett mechanism is an experimental system and due to the materials used, it is at its operating limit at a load of 3 kg (visible link deformation of about 1mm). While the collaborative robot UR3e is designed with a significant rigidity reserve when handling 3 kg. This is probably why, compared to earlier simulations, the energy consumed by the UR3e robot is different in units of percentages, while for the Bennett mechanism the energy consumption is noticeably different.

A. IMPACT OF TRAJECTORY ORIENTATION ON THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION

In the second experimental measurement, the goal was to investigate the effect of the orientation of the mechanism and therefore the orientation of the motion curve on the energy consumption. Because it has only one degree of freedom changes in orientation could have a significant effect. The final results can be seen in Figure 13 shows the average energy consumption E_{cycle} of both analyzed systems in different configurations and under different loads. The orientations are explained in the chapter IV-A.

Significant differences in the energy consumed can be observed in Figure 13 and Table 9. It is evident that the initial orientation of the mechanism also affects the energy consumption. Bennett's mechanism consumed the highest power in the vertical position (O_3) and the lowest in the horizontal position (O_2). In contrast, the UR3e robot showed stable behavior in all tested orientations.

TABLE 9. Electrical energy consumption per one cycle of motion for different orientations.

Energy consumption [J]	Mass of weight			
	1.0 kg	1.5 kg	2.0 kg	2.5 kg
Bennett O_1	23.6 ± 4.7	49.7 ± 7.5	74.3 ± 12.0	84.5 ± 11.5
Bennett O_2	3.9 ± 0.2	7.4 ± 1.2	12.7 ± 0.9	26.8 ± 3.5
Bennett O_3	92.3 ± 8.8	112.6 ± 11.6	139.7 ± 14.1	186.9 ± 18.1
UR3e O_1	448.7 ± 42.6	701.4 ± 38.6	986.5 ± 44.9	1273 ± 38.7
UR3e O_2	387.5 ± 25.7	658.7 ± 20.9	953.6 ± 37.6	1225 ± 30.9
UR3e O_3	498.4 ± 24.7	726.3 ± 21.7	1004 ± 36.5	1268 ± 26.7

FIGURE 13. Graphical illustration of data from Table 9 - comparison of measured energy consumption for different orientations per one cycle.

The largest energy saving was 98% of the original energy consumption of the UR3e robot and the average was a 92%

reduction in energy consumption. The presented results are only related to the tested structures, but suggest that most of these structures could be highly efficient and a very interesting choice for the future development of robotics.

A comparison of the energy consumption of both systems determined in simulations and measurements for a 2.5 kg load and orientation O_1 is shown in Table 10 and Figure 14. The results show a relatively high degree of agreement in the case of the UR3e collaborative robot. For the Bennett mechanism, the differences are significant, which is probably related to the fact that the model used in the simulations was significantly simplified compared to the prototype. Nevertheless, both the simulation and the experiment confirm that the mechanism consumed on average 92% less energy.

TABLE 10. Comparison energy consumption from software simulation and real experiment - per one cycle, clear weight 2.5 kg, orientation O_1 .

Energy consumption	Simul. [J]	Experiment [J]	Diff. [%]
Bennett mechanism	47.89	84.5 ± 11.5	76.5
UR3e original traj.	1 323	1 296 ± 20.8	2.0
UR3e interpol. traj.	1 306	1 273 ± 38.7	2.4

FIGURE 14. Graphical illustration of data from Table 10 - comparison energy consumption per one cycle, net weight 2.5 kg, orientation O_1 .

As noted earlier in comparison with the previously performed simulations, the values of the energy consumed by the UR3e robot are different in units of percentages, while for the Bennett mechanism, there is a visible difference.

Using the simulation data and measured real data, we can calculate the approximate mechanical efficiency of this particular kinematics of the Bennett mechanism η_{mech} as the division of the real energy consumption E_{cycle} and the simulated value E_{sim} ,

$$\eta_{mech} = \frac{E_{cycle}}{E_{sim}}. \tag{4}$$

The mechanical efficiency of the η_{mech} is around 57% at a load of 2.5 kg, and probably due to the increasing deformation of the links and therefore increasing friction in the bearings, the efficiency has a decreasing characteristic. This problem is mainly caused by the lower rigidity of the mechanical design due to the mechanical properties of the PETG material used

FIGURE 15. Approximate mechanical efficiency of this particular kinematics of Bennett’s mechanism, orientation O_1 .

in the prototype. The use of other materials, such as steel or aluminum, would likely increase mechanical efficiency even with higher loads. The full plot is shown in Figure 15.

The values presented in this subchapter were not the primary objective of the study. Rather, they serve to complement the insights gained from the main part of the research.

B. EVALUATION OF RESULTS

The large difference in energy consumption between the Bennett mechanism and the UR3e robot can be attributed to several structural factors. First, the Bennett mechanism requires only a single actuator, which eliminates most of the electrical and mechanical losses normally associated with driving multiple joints, such as resistive losses, gearbox friction or regenerative braking inefficiencies. Second, its closed-loop kinematic structure allows a substantial portion of the gravitational and inertial loads to be passively transferred through the links, instead of being actively compensated by motors. This significantly reduces the required joint torque. Third, the system moves considerably less mass than a serial robot, which lowers the inertial forces and further decreases energy demand, particularly during acceleration phases.

The influence of trajectory orientation also follows from these characteristics. In orientation O_3 , the motor must act directly against gravity over the full range of motion, leading to the highest energy consumption. In contrast, in orientation O_2 part of the gravitational load is absorbed structurally by the closed-loop configuration, which results in the lowest measured energy. The UR3e shows much weaker sensitivity to orientation, because gravity compensation is distributed across six powered joints, and the robot continuously compensates gravitational forces regardless of end effector orientation.

A similar pattern is observed with variations in payload. For the Bennett mechanism, increasing mass linearly increases the required driving torque, and simultaneously increases link deformation and bearing friction, which lowers mechanical efficiency. For the UR3e, the effect is less linear due to the interplay of several actuators and the internal gravity compensation model, but the overall trend also reflects increasing actuator effort.

These analyses explain why the Bennett mechanism shows such drastic reductions in energy consumption and highlight the structural and actuation-related principles behind its efficiency.

VI. CONCLUSION

The aim of this study was to design a mechatronic system based on Bennett's mechanism for pick-and-place applications and to compare its energy consumption with a commercial robotic system commonly used for such operations in practice. Comparisons were made between a prototype four-link Bennett mechanism with four rotary joints, which represented a closed kinematic structure with one degree of freedom, and a UR3e collaborative robot representing an open serial kinematic structure with six degrees of freedom. Unlike a universal robot, the Bennett mechanism can only perform one movement. The prototype mechanism was therefore designed for one specific trajectory, which was defined by a quadratic dual quaternion curve. The trajectory was selected based on simulations prior to the measurements.

Since these are fundamentally different systems, only the energy consumption related to the manipulated object was compared. This was achieved by subtracting the consumption of the system without load from the total consumption with load. The experimental measurements were designed to take into account the influence of load weight and trajectory orientation. The results showed a significant decrease in energy consumption (on average by more than 90%) in favor of the Bennett mechanism. In general, it can be said that mechanical systems with a closed kinematic loop and a single drive are suitable candidates for industrial applications in terms of energy efficiency, especially for pick-and-place operations. Despite these advantages, the Bennett mechanism also has several significant limitations. As a single-purpose device, it is restricted to a single predefined trajectory, and any modification of the task requires synthesizing a new kinematic structure. The workspace, orientation capability, and overall motion flexibility are therefore fundamentally constrained by the geometry of the linkage. In addition, practical industrial deployment may be challenging due to sensitivity to manufacturing tolerances, the need for precise calibration and limited adaptability to varying payloads. These factors highlight that, while extremely efficient, such mechanisms are not universal replacements for conventional robots and must be applied in carefully selected scenarios.

Further research should therefore focus on optimizing the stiffness of the structure and refining the control algorithms to improve overall efficiency, dynamic stability, and motion accuracy, and to ensure smooth behavior even at higher loads or speeds, especially when passing through singular positions. At the same time, it is advisable to explore the possibilities of system reconfigurability to increase the application range and adaptability of the manipulator to other operations. Mechanisms with a higher number of links, such as 6R links with one degree of freedom [27], [28],

or mechanisms with two degrees of freedom [29], are also a challenge for the future in order to assess their feasibility and energy efficiency in complex industrial applications.

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DANIEL HUCZALA received the Ph.D. degree in robotics from VSB–Technical University of Ostrava, in 2022. He is currently a Postdoctoral Researcher with the University of Innsbruck, focusing on geometry and theoretical kinematics. He specializes in modern design of single-loop mechanisms, covering their synthesis, self-intersection-free design, and control. In relation to that, he developed the rational linkages package, an open-source solution that simplifies the design, and prototyping of the mechanisms.

GRZEGORZ ORZECZOWSKI is currently an Associate Professor (Tenure Track) with the LUT Lahti Sustainable Mechatronics Mechanical Engineering. Specializing in modeling future machinery aims to enhance machine operations and benefit Finnish society. Committed to sustainable innovation, integrates AI, and intelligent systems to advance mechatronics.

AKI MIKKOLA is currently a Professor of mechanical engineering with LUT University, Finland, where he leads the research in multibody dynamics simulation. His work focuses on flexible multibody methods, digital twins, and real-time simulation for heavy machinery and sustainable engineering applications. He has published extensively and is active in international collaborations with both academia and industry.

ZDENKO BOBOVSKÝ is currently the Head of the Department of Robotics and a Full Professor of control systems and processes with VSB–Technical University of Ostrava. His research focuses on robot design and control. He has published more than 40 peer-reviewed articles, 11 conference papers, and successfully supervised six Ph.D. students, three of whom won Siemens Industry 4.0 Awards, from 2021 to 2023. Since 2024 he has been a Leading Research topics

in the large-scale projects REFRESH and MATUR, funded by Czech Ministry, and has co-authored publications with more than 70 international researchers.

TOMÁŠ POŠTULKA received the master's degree in robotics from the Technical University of Ostrava, in 2022, where he is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree. His current research interests focus on the Bennett mechanism with one degree of freedom and its potential for industry.

RÓBERT HUŇADY is currently an Associate Professor in applied mechanics. He is a Researcher and a Lecturer with VSB–Technical University Ostrava, where he leads the Laboratory of Experimental Robotics. His scientific focus is on the development and application of numerical and experimental methods of mechanics.

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